

The Effect of Green Cost, Digital Transformation, Sustainability Growth Rate, and Bank Characteristics Mediated by Good Corporate Governance on Banking Performance in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the effect of green cost, digital transformation, sustainability growth rate, and banking characteristics on banking performance, mediated by good corporate governance (GCG). This research employs a descriptive quantitative approach with a sample of 30 conventional banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the period 2019–2024. The analytical method used is panel data regression with EViews 13, employing the Random Effect Model (REM) as the most appropriate model, supported by the Sobel test for mediation analysis. The findings reveal that green cost, sustainability growth rate, non-performing loan, and good corporate governance (GCG) have a significant effect on banking performance. Furthermore, only non-performing loan significantly affects GCG. Meanwhile for indirect effects, GCG does not mediate the relationships between green cost, digital transformation, sustainability growth rate, third-party funds, non-performing loan, and capital adequacy ratio on banking performance, except in the cases of green cost (full mediation) and non-performing loan (partial mediation). These findings contribute to the banking management literature by emphasizing the importance of sustainable growth and effective GCG implementation. Limitations include a restricted sample size, which constrains the generalizability of results, as well as the presence of external factors such as varying macroeconomic conditions and regulatory environments across periods, which may impede the precise isolation of each independent variable's effect on banking performance.

KEYWORDS: green cost, digital transformation, sustainability growth rate, third-party funds, non-performing loans, capital adequacy ratio, good corporate governance

I. INTRODUCTION

The banking sector plays a fundamental role in supporting a country's economic growth through its intermediation function, mobilizing funds from the public and channelling them back into productive financing. This strategic role positions the banking sector as a primary pillar in maintaining financial system stability while simultaneously fostering sustainable economic activity (Xu, 2025). In Indonesia, the banking sector has demonstrated significant development, both in terms of the number of institutions and the scale of operations, with substantial contributions to national economic development.

Banking performance serves as an important indicator for assessing the health and operational effectiveness of banks. One of the most widely used measures is profitability, particularly Return on Assets (ROA), which reflects a bank's ability to generate profit from its assets (Alarussi & Gao, 2023). A high level of profitability indicates efficient resource management and the bank's capacity to create value for its stakeholders (Farhan & Zulfikar, 2024). However, banking performance is not always stable and is influenced by economic dynamics, regulatory changes, and shifting market behavior.

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic serves as a compelling example of how external factors can significantly affect banking performance. In 2020, bank profitability declined due to rising credit risk, loan restructuring, and reduced economic activity. Nevertheless, during the post-pandemic period, the banking sector demonstrated a notable recovery in line with increasing business activity and credit demand. This underscores that adaptive capacity and risk management are key factors in sustaining banking performance amid economic uncertainty.

In the context of global developments and technological advancement, the banking industry also faces new challenges, including the digitalization of services, evolving consumer preferences, and growing demands for sustainable business practices.

The Effect of Green Cost, Digital Transformation, Sustainability Growth Rate, and Bank Characteristics Mediated by Good Corporate Governance on Banking Performance in Indonesia

Regarding the concepts of green cost, digital transformation, and sustainability growth rate (SGR) have become relevant to examine banking performance. Green cost reflects a company's investment in environmentally oriented activities, such as emissions reduction, energy efficiency, and corporate social responsibility. The adoption of green cost not only contributes to environmental sustainability but may also enhance corporate reputation and reduce long-term risks (Zhang et al., 2022). However, several studies report mixed results, where environmental costs may be perceived as additional burdens that potentially compress short-term profitability (Wulandari et al., 2022).

Digital transformation has emerged as an unavoidable strategic factor in the modern banking industry. Digitalization enables banks to enhance operational efficiency, expand service access, and develop more competitive product innovations (Tran et al., 2023). The adoption of technologies such as mobile banking, fintech, and digital payment systems has fundamentally changed how banks interact with customers and improved service quality. Nevertheless, the impact of digital transformation on banking performance remains inconsistent across studies, with some finding a positive effect and others reporting a negative one (Huong et al., 2023).

Furthermore, sustainability growth rate (SGR) has emerged as an important indicator for assessing a firm's capacity to grow sustainably without excessive reliance on external financing (Agha, 2023). SGR reflects the balance between growth, profitability, and sound financial management. Although this concept holds high relevance in the context of business sustainability, empirical research on SGR in the banking sector remains relatively limited, thereby opening opportunities for further exploration.

On the other hand, risk and bank-specific characteristics also have a significant influence on financial performance. Indicators such as third-party funds (DPK), non-performing loan (NPL), and capital adequacy ratio (CAR) are critical variables in measuring banking stability and efficiency. DPK plays a role in enhancing financing capacity and profitability, while NPL reflects credit risk that can erode performance if poorly managed. CAR, as a capital adequacy indicator, demonstrates a bank's ability to withstand risk and sustain operational stability (Dewi & Ghalib, 2024; Aishya et al., 2022).

Beyond these factors, good corporate governance (GCG) constitutes an essential element in enhancing banking performance. Effective GCG implementation improves transparency, accountability, and stakeholder trust. One pertinent GCG mechanism is executive compensation, designed to align managerial interests with those of shareholders. However, executive compensation may also give rise to opportunistic behavior if not properly structured (Mohammed et al., 2023; Ali & Chouaibi, 2023).

Based on the foregoing review, it is evident that banking performance is influenced by a complex and interrelated set of factors encompassing environmental sustainability, digital transformation, sustainable growth, financial characteristics, and corporate governance. However, prior research continues to show inconsistencies, and there remains a limited number of studies that integrate all these factors within a single comprehensive research model.

This study aims to empirically examine the effect of green cost, digital transformation, sustainability growth rate, and bank characteristics on banking performance in Indonesia, incorporating good corporate governance, proxied through executive compensation as a mediating variable. This research is expected to contribute to enriching the literature and providing practical implications for strategic decision-making in the banking sector.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Green Cost and Banking Performance

Green cost refers to expenditures incurred by banks in support of environmentally sustainable activities, including green financing, eco-friendly operations, and compliance with environmental, social, and governance (ESG) regulations (Qian & Yu, 2024). From a stakeholder theory perspective, environmental investments reflect corporate social responsibility and can enhance reputation and public trust. Prior research suggests that green cost can improve financial performance through reputational gains and operational efficiency (Zhang et al., 2022; Husain et al., 2025; Aliamutu et al., 2023; Nguyen et al., 2024). Moreover, firms with consistent environmental activities tend to have stronger relationships with stakeholders, which positively affects long-term profitability (Tai, 2022).

H1: Green cost has a positive effect on banking performance.

2.2. Digital Transformation and Banking Performance

Digital transformation is the process of adopting digital technologies in banking systems, products, and services to enhance operational efficiency and competitiveness (Kardiman et al., 2025). This transformation encompasses the use of mobile banking, big data, artificial intelligence, and other digital technologies. Theoretically, digital transformation improves efficiency, expands

The Effect of Green Cost, Digital Transformation, Sustainability Growth Rate, and Bank Characteristics Mediated by Good Corporate Governance on Banking Performance in Indonesia

service access, and fosters product innovation (Tran et al., 2023; Do et al., 2022; Abdurrahman et al., 2024; Awwad & El Khoury, 2024). Empirical studies indicate that digitalization positively affects banking performance through increased productivity and customer satisfaction (Trimulyana, 2024; Aljawarneh, 2024).

H2: Digital transformation has a positive effect on banking performance.

2.3. Sustainability Growth Rate and Banking Performance

Sustainability Growth Rate (SGR) is the maximum rate of growth a firm can achieve without substantially increasing external leverage (Ndalamba & Manuel, 2025). SGR reflects a company's ability to maintain stable and sustainable growth. Research indicates that SGR has a positive effect on profitability, as it reflects efficient financial management and sound growth strategy (Agha, 2023; Ariesa et al., 2023; Madbouly, 2022; Wassef et al., 2024). Firms with high SGR tend to be more stable and exhibit superior financial performance.

H3: Sustainability growth rate has a positive effect on banking performance.

2.4. Third-Party Funds (DPK) and Banking Performance

Third-party funds (DPK) represent funds mobilized from the public in the form of savings, current accounts, and time deposits (Ariyadi & Riyanto, 2022; Tho'in & Heliawan, 2020). DPK constitutes the primary source of bank funding for intermediation activities. A larger DPK base increases a bank's capacity to extend credit and generate income (Komaria et al., 2024; Farhan & Zulfikar, 2024; Dewi & Ghalib, 2024; Sitanggang & Wahyuni, 2024). Accordingly, DPK makes a direct contribution to improving bank profitability.

H4: Third-party funds have a positive effect on banking performance.

2.5. Non-Performing Loan and Banking Performance

Non-performing loan (NPL) is the ratio of problem loans reflecting borrower default risk (Idris et al., 2025). A high NPL ratio indicates poor credit management quality. Research shows that NPL negatively affects profitability by increasing provisioning costs and reducing interest income (Maula et al., 2024; Karim et al., 2023; Kurniawan et al., 2020; Mpofu & Nikolaidou, 2018).

H5: Non-performing loan has a negative effect on banking performance.

2.6. Capital Adequacy Ratio and Banking Performance

Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is a ratio indicating a bank's ability to absorb potential losses (Setiawan & Muchtar, 2021). CAR reflects the strength of a bank's capital position. Research shows that CAR positively affects performance by enhancing a bank's capacity to manage risk and expand its business (Fauji & Oktafiani, 2022; Komaria et al., 2024; Iklin, 2023; Yudianto et al., 2024).

H6: Capital adequacy ratio has a positive effect on banking performance.

2.7. Good Corporate Governance and Banking Performance

Good Corporate Governance (GCG) is a corporate governance system that ensures transparency, accountability, and fairness (Asnatang et al., 2025). Effective GCG implementation increases investor confidence and operational efficiency (Andriyani et al., 2022; Rizki & Wuryani, 2021; Boshnak et al., 2023; Bui & Krajcsák, 2024). As such, GCG makes a direct contribution to improving banking performance.

H7: Good corporate governance has a positive effect on banking performance.

2.8. Green Cost and Good Corporate Governance

Green cost represents expenditures by companies in support of environmentally friendly activities and sustainability (Qian & Yu, 2024). Under stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984), environmental investments reflect a firm's commitment to transparency and social responsibility, core pillars of GCG. Research indicates that environmental expenditures promote improvements in corporate governance quality through enhanced transparency and accountability (Wiguna et al., 2023; Amelia, 2024; Peng et al., 2025; Wang et al., 2025). Furthermore, sound sustainability practices strengthen investor trust and improve the quality of corporate reporting (Xiao & Su, 2025).

H8: Green cost has a positive effect on good corporate governance.

2.9. Digital Transformation and Good Corporate Governance

Digital transformation encompasses the integration of digital technology across all business processes of a firm (Kardiman et al., 2025). This transformation not only enhances efficiency but also strengthens internal transparency and oversight. Research shows that digitalization can reduce information asymmetry and improve the effectiveness of corporate governance (Budiman, 2024; Sun & Guo, 2024; Li & Sen, 2021; Goldstein et al., 2021). Additionally, digital technologies improve the quality of decision-making and organizational accountability (Yu et al., 2022).

The Effect of Green Cost, Digital Transformation, Sustainability Growth Rate, and Bank Characteristics Mediated by Good Corporate Governance on Banking Performance in Indonesia

H9: Digital transformation has a positive effect on good corporate governance.

2.10. Sustainability Growth Rate and Good Corporate Governance

Sustainability Growth Rate (SGR) reflects a firm's ability to sustain stable and continuous growth (Ndalamba & Manuel, 2025). Within the agency theory framework (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), sound governance ensures efficient resource utilization and mitigates conflicts of interest. Research suggests that firms with high sustainable growth rates tend to exhibit better governance practices (Kalia & Gill, 2023; Parapat et al., 2024; Lusmeida et al., 2023; Agha, 2023).

H10: Sustainability growth rate has a positive effect on good corporate governance.

2.11. Third-Party Funds and Good Corporate Governance

Third-party funds (DPK) represent public deposits that reflect the level of public trust in the bank (Ariyadi & Riyanto, 2022). High DPK signals strong bank credibility and reputation. Research indicates that increases in DPK are associated with higher governance quality, as public trust incentivizes greater transparency and accountability (Saputra et al., 2024; Puspitasari et al., 2020; Juliasari, 2020; Fu et al., 2021).

H11: Third-party funds have a positive effect on good corporate governance.

2.12. Non-Performing Loan and Good Corporate Governance

Non-performing loan (NPL) reflects the level of credit risk in banking (Idris et al., 2025). A high NPL indicates weak oversight and risk management. Research shows that high NPL is negatively correlated with the quality of corporate governance (Nurkhin et al., 2024; Usmawati et al., 2023; Hanzl & Gerstmayr, 2024; Colonnello et al., 2023).

H12: Non-performing loan has a negative effect on good corporate governance.

2.13. Capital Adequacy Ratio and Good Corporate Governance

Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) reflects a bank's ability to absorb risk and maintain financial stability. A high CAR indicates sound risk management. Research shows that CAR is positively associated with governance quality, as it reflects managerial discipline and risk control (Jagirani et al., 2023; Maknuun et al., 2024; Jiang et al., 2024; Colonnello et al., 2022).

H13: Capital adequacy ratio has a positive effect on good corporate governance.

2.14. Mediation of Good Corporate Governance (GCG)

Green cost management supported by GCG enables firms to transform environmental investments into economic value. Research shows that GCG mediates the relationship between environmental costs and firm performance (**H14**) (Miladiazari et al., 2021; Fitriyani & Sungkar, 2024). Digital transformation enhances governance effectiveness, which in turn improves firm performance (**H15**) (Lee & Choi, 2021; Wang & Yang, 2024). SGR reflects sustainable growth supported by sound governance (**H16**) (Arslan & Alqatan, 2020). High DPK reflects public trust reinforced by strong governance, ultimately improving performance (**H17**) (Akbar, 2020). Effective GCG mitigates the adverse effect of NPL on performance (**H18**) (Rachman & Tristanto, 2024). A high CAR, managed through strong governance, further optimizes performance (**H19**) (Abraar et al., 2024; Simatupang & Prabowo, 2021).

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a quantitative approach with the objective of testing hypotheses through causal relationship analysis among variables. A causal design is applied to explain the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable, where changes in the independent variables are assumed to cause changes in the dependent variable (Hardani et al., 2020). Secondary data were obtained from official sources, including Bank Indonesia, the Indonesian Banking Statistics (Statistik Perbankan Indonesia/SPI) published by the Financial Services Authority (Otoritas Jasa Keuangan/OJK), and annual financial reports of each bank publicly accessible through the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the period 2019–2024.

The population of this study consists of all conventional commercial banks listed on the IDX. Purposive sampling was employed as the sampling technique, selecting samples based on predetermined criteria relevant to the research objectives. Based on the established criteria, a final sample of 30 banking companies was obtained from a total population of 48 companies, covering a six-year observation period (2019–2024). Data analysis employed panel data regression combined with path analysis to examine both direct and indirect relationships among variables, using the Sobel test for mediation testing. Panel data was selected for its advantages in increasing the number of observations, reducing multicollinearity issues, and providing more efficient estimates (Gujarati & Porter, 2020). Data processing was conducted using E-Views 13 software.

The empirical model consists of two regression equations. The first model tests the direct effect of independent variables and the mediating variable on banking performance proxied by Return on Assets (ROA):

The Effect of Green Cost, Digital Transformation, Sustainability Growth Rate, and Bank Characteristics Mediated by Good Corporate Governance on Banking Performance in Indonesia

$$ROA_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 GC_{it} + \beta_2 DT_{it} + \beta_3 SGR_{it} + \beta_4 DPK_{it} + \beta_5 NPL_{it} + \beta_6 CAR_{it} + \beta_7 GCG_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots(1)$$

The second model examines the effect of independent variables on the Good Corporate Governance (GCG) mediating variable:

$$GCG_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 GC_{it} + \beta_2 DT_{it} + \beta_3 SGR_{it} + \beta_4 DPK_{it} + \beta_5 NPL_{it} + \beta_6 CAR_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots(2)$$

Where: ROA_{it} = Return on Assets; GC_{it} = Green Cost; DT_{it} = Digital Transformation; SGR_{it} = Sustainability Growth Rate; DPK_{it} = Third-Party Funds; NPL_{it} = Non-Performing Loan; CAR_{it} = Capital Adequacy Ratio; GCG_{it} = Good Corporate Governance; for firm *i* in year *t*.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive analysis is used to summarize the characteristics of the research sample, including minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation values. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistical results for 30 conventional banks in Indonesia over the period 2019–2024.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev
GC	3.004574	0.003486	365.9134	-0.019081	28.00146
DT	0.090200	0.034337	0.950503	0.000114	0.155093
SGR	9.364446	6.187708	83.55966	-89.11028	20.34888
DPK	262.9933	19.16969	8216.000	3.68E-05	1080.724
NPL	1.465333	1.005000	4.960000	0.040000	1.182465
CAR	29.44633	24.23500	127.4200	8.220000	17.39994
GCG	10.44606	10.55000	12.96000	6.010000	1.095575
ROA	1.122611	1.300000	4.220000	-13.60000	2.105666

Source: E-Views 13 Output

The descriptive statistics reveal that the overall fundamental condition of the Indonesian banking sector is reasonably sound, though certain disparities exist across banks. The green cost (GC) variable has a mean of 3.00 with a high standard deviation, suggesting that the allocation of expenditures for environmentally oriented activities remains relatively small and has yet to emerge as a primary operational priority. Meanwhile, the digital transformation (DT) variable has a mean of 0.09, indicating that the level of digital technology adoption is still at a low to moderate stage and unevenly distributed across banks.

In terms of growth, the sustainability growth rate (SGR) has a mean of 9.36 with considerable variation, reflecting disparities in banks' capacity to sustain balanced growth. This suggests that financial management strategies, operational efficiency, and dividend policies play important roles in determining the sustainability of bank growth. On the other hand, third-party funds (DPK) show a relatively high mean of 262.99, reflecting the banking sector's ability to mobilize public funds and a relatively strong level of public trust.

With respect to risk and capital adequacy, the non-performing loan (NPL) ratio has a mean of 1.46, below the maximum threshold of 5%, indicating that banks are generally capable of managing credit risk effectively. The capital adequacy ratio (CAR) shows a mean of 29.44, substantially above the regulatory minimum, signalling that the banking sector maintains a strong capital position to absorb risk and support business expansion. The good corporate governance (GCG) variable has a mean of 10.44, indicating that corporate governance practices are at a moderately good level.

Banking performance measured by ROA shows a mean of 1.12, suggesting that the banking industry is broadly capable of generating positive profitability. However, a considerably low minimum value indicates the presence of some banks with weak or negative performance, reflecting differences in asset management, operational efficiency, and credit quality across institutions. Overall, these findings suggest that while the Indonesian banking sector's fundamentals are relatively strong, challenges remain in the areas of sustainability, digitalization, and cross-bank performance disparities.

4.2. Regression Analysis Results

Table 2 presents the summary of regression results for this study.

Table 2. Summary of Regression Results				
Independent Variable	ROA		GCG	
	Coef.	Prob.	Coef.	Prob.
C	-3.736540	-	2.005245	-

The Effect of Green Cost, Digital Transformation, Sustainability Growth Rate, and Bank Characteristics Mediated by Good Corporate Governance on Banking Performance in Indonesia

GC	-0.000679	0.5795	-0.000420	0.0385
DT	-0.378463	0.3259	-0.020648	0.6479
SGR	0.021171	0.0004***	-0.000239	0.5534
DPK	0.664753	0.0839	0.135620	0.0003***
NPL	-0.423403	0.0024***	-0.036786	0.0090***
CAR	0.009684	0.0216**	0.000150	0.7448
GCG	-0.240154	0.3464	-	-
Adj R-Square	0,819367		0,066844	
Prob F stat	0,000000		0,006057	
Selected Model	FEM		REM	

Note: ** significant at 5%; *** significant at 1%. Source: E-Views 13 Output

Furthermore, the Sobel test was applied to examine whether GCG mediates the relationships between independent variables and ROA.

Table 3. Sobel Test Result

Indirect Effect Pathway	Test Statistic	Std. Error	P-value
GC → GCG → ROA	1,99470751	0,00005057	0,0460
DT → GCG → ROA	0,45601005	0,0108741	0,6483
SGR → GCG → ROA	0,59126331	9,707E-05	0,5543
DPK → GCG → ROA	-3,06850434	0,0106142	0,0021
NPL → GCG → ROA	2,39393186	0,0036903	0,0166
CAR → GCG → ROA	-0,32414063	0,0001111	0,7458

Source: Calculator Sobel Test Output, 2025

4.3. Discussion

1. Green Cost and Banking Performance.

The empirical results indicate that green cost does not significantly influence banking performance as measured by Return on Assets (ROA). This finding is consistent with Asjuwita & Agustin (2020) and Gutiérrez-Ponce & Wibowo (2023), who demonstrated that environmental expenditures tend to suppress short-term profitability when not yet integrated with core business strategies. In the banking sector, green cost is largely associated with CSR programs and sustainability compliance rather than direct revenue-generating activities, producing benefits, such as reputational gains and stakeholder trust, that manifest over longer time horizons. This contrasts with studies by Widjaya & Nursiam (2024) and Rosmanidar et al. (2024), whose findings suggest that strategically managed environmental costs can enhance firm value and financial performance.

2. Digital Transformation and Banking Performance.

Digital transformation shows no significant direct effect on ROA. Although theoretical frameworks posit that digital adoption improves operational efficiency and market reach (Vial, 2019; Do et al., 2022), the results suggest that its benefits in the Indonesian banking sector have yet to materialize within the observation period. This aligns with study done by Brahmana & Kontesa (2024) and contrasts with Tran et al. (2023) and Nguyen et al. (2023). The non-significant relationship may be attributable to uneven digital adoption among customers, high implementation costs, and the absence of complementary organizational transformation in governance and human capital capacity.

3. Sustainability Growth Rate and Banking Performance.

Sustainability Growth Rate (SGR) demonstrates a significant positive effect on ROA, confirming that banks capable of sustaining balanced growth, without reliance on external financing achieve superior financial performance. Rooted in Higgins' (1981) framework, SGR captures the interplay between profitability, dividend policy, leverage, and asset efficiency. These findings corroborate Ariesa et al. (2023), Manullang & Hutabarat (2020), and Wassef et al. (2024), underscoring that sustainable financial growth directly drives banking profitability.

4. Third-Party Funds (DPK) and Banking Performance.

Third-party funds (DPK) show no significant direct effect on ROA. While DPK represents the primary funding source for bank intermediation, the results suggest that fund mobilization does not translate into higher profitability unless effectively deployed through quality credit and productive investment. This finding aligns with Marbun & Khairunnisa (2023) and diverges from Komaria et al. (2024) and Farhan & Zulfikar (2024), reinforcing that the intermediation efficiency, not mere fund accumulation is the critical determinant of performance.

The Effect of Green Cost, Digital Transformation, Sustainability Growth Rate, and Bank Characteristics Mediated by Good Corporate Governance on Banking Performance in Indonesia

5. Non-Performing Loan (NPL) and Banking Performance.

NPL show a significant negative effect on ROA, consistent with regulatory standards (OJK, POJK No. 4/2016) prescribing an NPL threshold below 5%. Elevated credit risk reduces interest income, necessitates higher loan-loss provisioning, and deteriorates asset quality. These results are consistent with Kinanti & Putra (2024), Maula et al. (2024), and Paparo et al. (2024), collectively affirming NPL as a primary determinant of banking profitability.

6. Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) and Banking Performance.

CAR shows a significant positive effect on ROA, indicating that well-capitalized banks are better positioned to absorb risks and pursue credit expansion and productive investment. This finding aligns with BIS minimum capital adequacy standards and is supported by Ghosh & Mondal (2022), Komaria et al. (2024), and Dewi & Ghalib (2024). Adequate capitalization strengthens investor confidence and ensures operational resilience.

7. Good Corporate Governance (GCG) as a Direct Determinant.

GCG, proxied through executive compensation, did not directly influence ROA. While agency theory posits that well-designed incentive structures align managerial behavior with shareholder interests (Mohammed et al., 2023), compensation-based governance may not sufficiently capture the breadth of governance quality needed to drive short-term financial performance. This is consistent with Natto & Mokoaleli-Mokoteli (2025) and Puspita & Wenny (2024).

8. Mediation Effects of GCG.

Sobel tests reveal that GCG fully mediates the relationship between green cost and ROA (H14 supported), while partially mediating the NPL-ROA relationship (H18 supported). In the green cost pathway, GCG transforms environmental expenditure from an operational cost burden into a strategic investment by aligning sustainability initiatives with governance mechanisms, corroborating Miladiasari et al. (2021) and Fitriyani & Sungkar (2024). In the NPL pathway, effective governance partially attenuates the negative impact of credit risk on performance through stronger internal oversight, prudential lending standards, and transparent risk management, consistent with Rachman & Tristanto (2024) and Khayidah et al. (2024). GCG did not mediate the pathways involving digital transformation, SGR, DPK, or CAR, suggesting these variables exert their effects on performance through more direct financial and operational channels.

CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the determinants of banking performance (ROA) across Indonesian commercial banks, incorporating green cost, digital transformation, sustainability growth rate, third-party funds (DPK), non-performing loan (NPL), capital adequacy ratio (CAR), and good corporate governance (GCG) as both direct and mediating variables. The findings demonstrate that internal financial factors specifically SGR, NPL, and CAR are the dominant determinants of banking performance. SGR positively drives profitability through disciplined financial growth management, CAR strengthens performance from risk absorption capacity, while NPL exerts the strongest adverse effect by eroding asset quality and compressing net income.

On the other hand, green cost, digital transformation, DPK, and GCG do not exhibit significant direct effects on ROA within the study period. These variables appear to operate on longer time horizons or require integration with complementary organizational and strategic factors to produce measurable financial outcomes.

Furthermore, GCG functions as an effective mediating mechanism only in specific pathways: it fully mediates the green cost–performance relationship and partially mediates the NPL–performance relationship. These results imply that governance quality is a necessary but not universally sufficient conduit for translating firm-level strategic and risk variables into financial performance improvements.

The practical implication for Indonesian banking institutions is clear: while embracing sustainability initiatives and digital transformation remains strategically imperative, these efforts must be anchored in robust governance frameworks, prudent credit risk management, adequate capitalization, and sustainable growth discipline to yield tangible improvements in financial performance.

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The Effect of Green Cost, Digital Transformation, Sustainability Growth Rate, and Bank Characteristics Mediated by Good Corporate Governance on Banking Performance in Indonesia

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The Effect of Green Cost, Digital Transformation, Sustainability Growth Rate, and Bank Characteristics Mediated by Good Corporate Governance on Banking Performance in Indonesia

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